

D6.3

***T6.3 Report* Report on Harvesting Workshops proceedings**

CONEXUS

Urban nature connects us
Conectados por la naturaleza urbana
Conectados pela natureza urbana

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Table of contents

Introduction	5
1.The Engine Room from Task 6.3a	6
1.1. What is the Engine Room	6
1.2. Engine Room development process: First Phase	6
1.2.1. Buenos Aires Workshop	7
1.3. Engine Room development process: Second Phase	9
1.4. Role of Engine Room Animateur, Facilitation and Product development	10
2.The Harvesting Workshops from Task 6.3 b	11
2.1 Introduction to the CONEXUS Harvesting Workshops	11
2.2 São Paulo Harvesting Workshop	12
2.3 Turin Harvesting Workshop	16
2.4 Products Developed through the Engine Room/Harvesting Workshop	18
Conclusion	21
Annex.....	21

Table of figures

Figure 1 MURAL with the outcomes of the ER discussions	7
Figure 2 Ecosystem of guidelines diagram	8
Figure 3 Presentation of the Engine Room functionalities.....	10
Figure 4 Harvesting Workshop guidelines	12
Figure 5 Products display on the Engine Room Website	20

Introduction

This report presents the methodology, development, and achievements of the CONEXUS Work Package 6 “Hubbing: Sharing and Clustering” (Lead: EUKN, M1-48) and specifically within Task 6.3 “Co-Producing”, led by ICLEI with GV & OPPLA. This task is composed of two parts: 6.3 (a) “**Fuelling a co-productive CONEXUS Engine Room**”, and 6.3 (b) “**Harvesting Workshops**”, both focused on designing CONEXUS products tailored to the project’s targeted audience.

As a platform for product development and collaboration, the Engine Room provided an online forum for consortium partners to co-produce and stress-test CONEXUS end-user products. It acted as a hub where Work Package leaders, cities, and other partners actively engaged in discussions and exchanges related to product development. These discussions were key in the selection process of products to be evaluated during the Harvesting Workshops. During the workshops, products identified and refined in the Engine Room were further assessed for their market potential and practical applicability. Input gathered during the Harvesting Workshops was then fed back into the Engine Room, where it informed further product refinement and development. This iterative process ensured that CONEXUS products were not only informed by diverse local realities and needs but also evaluated through collaborative efforts within the consortium. Thus, the Engine Room and Harvesting Workshops worked hand in hand to drive innovation and ensure the relevance and effectiveness of CONEXUS end-user products in contributing to sustainable urban development.

1. The Engine Room from Task 6.3a

1.1. What is the Engine Room

The Engine Room represents a cornerstone in the innovative dialogue and development of CONEXUS products. It has also played a key role in the development and organisation of the Harvesting Workshops by selecting which products were mature enough to assess their market potential. The Engine Room is a project internal online forum for consortium partners to co-produce and stress-test CONEXUS end-user products. Work Package (WP) leaders, cities, and other partners actively participate in this vibrant space, ensuring that product development is both informed by and adaptable to diverse local realities and contexts. Hosted by OPPLA, this internal platform provides a virtual open space for exchanges, supplemented as necessary by additional group work, teleconferences and email exchanges. To function, project partners must take content ownership of the products that are based on their outcomes, and actively collaborate with their expertise in products from other partners.

For easier understanding of this document, here a list of the work package names within the CONEXUS project:

WP1: Engaging: Growing-Extending-Marketing

WP2: Contextualising-Integrating-Planning

WP3: Restoring: demonstrating place-based NBS

WP4: Analysing-Synthesising-Guiding

WP5: Valorising-Investing

WP6: Hubbing: Sharing and Clustering

WP7: Leading and Managing

1.2. Engine Room development process: First Phase

The Engine Room commenced in October 2021, through the promotion of regular online meetings among WP and tasks leaders aiming at developing impactful project resources to support the project's dissemination, exploitation and communication. For this first phase of the Engine Room, a two-way, integrated approach has been developed, working iteratively between WPs expert knowledge on the need for NbS products, coupled with end-users demands for products, from various sectors. Meetings were held to identify and establish key types of products needed, such as policy briefs, videos, podcasts, tools, decision-support assets and underpinning data. These discussions were strongly grounded in partners' knowledge about what makes products usable and used, holding important insights into pathways to impact with NbS.

Originally, the Grant Agreement listed potential CONEXUS products, including brochures, stakeholder engagement materials, and ICT applications, among others. However, the project's trajectory evolved,

leading to a revised list of products that were developed to address emerging themes and needs. The initial list of products included:

- A brochure on “Nature-based solutions for young audiences” derived from WP1.
- Stakeholder engagement materials, needs analyses, and decision-support tools.
- A portfolio of NbS case studies from cities across the EU and CELAC regions.
- Web-based information and lessons on nature-based thinking (NBT).
- A leaflet detailing participatory workshop processes.
- Information and communication Technologies (ICT) applications to provide an open platform for information.
- The CONEXUS participatory framework for analysis and assessment of NbS.
- Tools and data for cost-benefit analysis (CBA) and Socially responsible investing (SRI), along with a pamphlet on NbS business cases.

Throughout this first phase of the Engine Room, ICLEI Europe facilitated a series of online meetings, where WP and Task leaders identified, prioritised, and started designing potential end-user products. During those meetings, several potential products were identified. **Each WP then prioritised one product (a total of 6) to be tested during the first Harvesting Workshop in São Paulo.**

PRODUCTS	PRODUCT DETAILS	WP SYNERGIES	TARGET AUDIENCE
Communication materials 	Videos & Podcasts Branding of life labs	WP1, WP3, WP4 WP1, WP3	
Guidelines 	Technical/adapted to local context Cost-benefit/valuation Governance/advocacy 	WP4, WP2, WP3 WP4, WP5, WP2 WP4, WP3, WP6	
Capacity-building materials	Technical/adapted to local context Cost-benefit/valuation Governance/advocacy/participation 	WP1, WP2, WP4 WP1, WP5 WP1, WP3, WP6	
Exchange Platforms	Life labs Communities of practice 	WP3, WP6 WP6, WP3	
Policy briefs	SDGs/NUA goals through NBS Cost-benefit/valuation	WP6 WP5, WP1	

Figure 1 MURAL with the outcomes of the ER discussions

1.2.1. Buenos Aires Workshop

After reviewing the discussions and outcomes of the Engine Room online meetings, a workshop was conducted by partners of WP4 on Analysing-Synthesising-Guiding in the framework of T4.3 during the Buenos Aires Co-learning Forum (CLF) in October 2022. This workshop aimed to discuss and refine a

comprehensive list of potential products with project partners. Subsequently, based on the findings of the Workshop, throughout the first trimester of 2023, partners from WP6 (through T6.3) and WP4 (through T4.3) collaborated to determine which products would be suitable for inclusion in the Ecosystems of Guidelines (EoG), led by WP4 (within T4.3), and which would be managed and coordinated by the Engine Room. As a result of these alignments, a factsheet series was designated as a product developed under T4.3, while it was agreed that other products such as dissemination videos, policy briefs, and booklets would be developed under T6.3.

Figure 2 Ecosystem of guidelines diagram

This agreement marked the conclusion of the first stage of the Engine Room, with the following achievements: (i) definition and prioritisation of end-user products to be produced across WP; (ii) testing a set of products during the First Harvesting Workshop; (iii) further development of products in collaboration with T4.3; (iv) launch of videos in WP1.

Product	Audience	Content	Format	Synergies	Intended Impact	Potential Challenges
Infographics	General public	NbS concept	Infographics	All tasks	Support project deliverables and outcomes with visual materials,	Low demand for materials coming from partners
GIS Web Tool	Practitioners, Policy-makers	Spatial data analysis (land use, GB Infrastructure, Biodiversity)	Interactive/open GIS web tool	WP3 (T3.3)	Allow data comparison among pilots, give visibility to CONEXUS scientific results, improve understanding urban/environmental conditions	Data availability and access, lack of appropriated technical infrastructure and financial resources

Guideline: How to set a LL?	Practitioners, communities, local governments, NGO	Processes & lessons learned from CONEXUS LL	Factsheet Brochure	WP6, WP4 (4.2)	Reference material to support implementation of LL in different settings	Engagement of consortium partners to develop content
NbS Guidance Repository	Practitioners, governments, NGO, communities	List of NbS guidelines/resources on LA and EU	Online repository		Facilitate search and access to available NbS guidelines and resources	Infrastructure of CONEXUS webpage need to be adjusted to accommodate the repository
NbS Business Cases	Practitioners, governments, NGO, communities	Ecosystems services modelling, economic valuation, marketing strategies	Factsheet Brochure	WP6	Support local governments and NbS initiatives to secure investments and resources for NbS implementation in pilots	Availability of data on the inputs/outputs of the activities, and local capacity to support economic valuation and valorisation
(Digital) Co-Learning Framework	Communities, Multi-stakeholders assembly	Co-learning principles on digital environments	Handbook	WP1, WP2, T4.2 (M18)	Equalising directions of learning to balance power distribution between marginalised cultures/actors and dominant ones.	Partners adherence to co-learning principles, creating space for critical reflection and review.
Policy Brief on NbS & SDG	Policy-makers, investors	NbS contributions to the global goals (SDGs) & evidence generated on Pilots	Policy Brief	WP1 & WP4	To generate evidence on NbS contributions to the SDG for making the case for investments and business plans	Availability of data and issues with indicators measuring
Investment road-map	Life-lab, fund seekers	Decision tree to support finding potential funding sources for NbS projects	Digital tool available on CONEXUS website	WP5	Assist Life-Labs to find suitable funding opportunities for their initiatives	Potential bias and euro-centric retrievals/ Update funding opportunities & long term maintenance

Table 1 Products examples defined at the end of the first phase of the Engine Room, wrapping-up São Paulo Harvesting Workshop and Buenos Aires EoG Workshop results.

1.3. Engine Room development process: Second Phase

For the second stage of the Engine Room process, OPPLA designed an [internal online platform](#) launched at the Santiago online CLF 10th May 2023 This internal platform was considered by consortium partners to be crucial for collaboratively generating knowledge, co-producing, and rigorously testing new CONEXUS offerings in a digital environment that supports transdisciplinary

collaboration. An Engine Room Handbook was produced by Oppla to ensure a clear understanding of the use and functions of the platform (see Annex).

Register as an engine room user

To register as a user you must be a member of the Conexus consortium

Email:

- Full name
- Organisation
- Email address

engine@conexusnbs.com

Functionality of the engine room

Interacting in the engine room

- Join a group to enable you to join in the discussion
- Product leads and group members are displayed for each product so we all know who we are collaborating with
- Please upload your photograph when you complete your registration

Interacting in the engine room

Figure 3 Presentation of the Engine Room functionalities

The initial products introduced to the Engine Room were those evaluated during the São Paulo Harvesting Workshop in May 2022 **Products not subjected to testing at the São Paulo’s Harvesting Workshop underwent evaluation during the workshop in Torino, including (i) a series of policy briefs produced in collaboration with the CONEXUS Life-Labs (see Annex), and (ii) a series of publications related to the Co-Learning methodology developed by the project partner Living Cities (LCS).**

1.4. Role of Engine Room Animateur, Facilitation and Product development

ICLEI has been instrumental in facilitating the interactions within the Engine Room, focusing on the potential products' refinement and development. Grupo Verde / The Latin American Landscape Initiative (GV/LALI), partners within WP6, has played a critical role in transforming the working documents and partners' exchanges into finalised products, which were shared with OPPLA, the WP 1 lead to be disseminated through various channels, including events organised under WP1.

ICLEI South America (SAMS) has served as the animateur of the platform, playing a crucial role in fostering engagement and productive discussions among the partners. The animateur’s responsibilities included facilitating dialogue, ensuring that all voices were heard, and that the development process was inclusive and reflective of the diverse perspectives within the consortium.

Partners regularly received updates on topics and formats tailored to their specific local contexts, thus assisting in the development of products that addressed their unique circumstances.

In relation to the Engine Room two challenges have been identified: (i) the application of General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) to the consortium partners; (ii) insufficient Person Months (PMs) assigned to project partners to develop end-user products. Regarding the first point, the online platform was designed considering that a facilitator (the animateur) would send a monthly digest and updates of its discussion, and address project partners whenever their contributions were specifically required in a product discussion or formulation. However, due to GDPR norms, partners' email access could not be shared among the consortium. For this reason, the animation and facilitation of the Engine Room did not occur as originally planned and encountered some challenges in engaging consortium partners in discussions. To address this issue, several measures were taken, including reaching out to partners through alternative channels such as social media platforms like LinkedIn or WhatsApp, to ensure a level of engagement.

Relative to the PMs, WP leaders could more easily leverage their PM in other WPs to participate in the Engine Room meetings and first brainstorm on product ideas. Task leaders and general consortium partners interested in developing tools and exploitable end-user products had a tighter allocation of PMs for this purpose. As a result, some potential products identified in the Grant Agreement and discussed in the Engine Room throughout 2022 could not progress as much as the consortium had hoped. An important lesson can be drawn from that when designing proposals with ambitious exploitation outcomes: task leaders and project partners should have sufficient PMs to develop end-user products that require additional capacity investment.

2. The Harvesting Workshops from Task 6.3 b

2.1 Introduction to the CONEXUS Harvesting Workshops

Two Harvesting Workshops, orchestrated by ICLEI, were designed to gather best practices and critically assess the market potential of CONEXUS products. These workshops, held back-to-back to the annual CONEXUS General Assemblies (GABs) in São Paulo May 2022 and in Turin October 2023 aimed to foster a creative atmosphere conducive to innovation. Through active listening and reflective questioning, participants discussed practical applications and marketability of potential products.

Given that the GABs were internal events, the feedback on the proposed CONEXUS products was primarily sourced from within the consortium, involving partners who were intimately familiar with the project's goals and the needs of its target audiences. While this ensured a high level of expertise and relevance in the feedback provided, it also limited the scope of perspectives considered during these sessions.

Unfortunately, logistical constraints and the project's internal focus precluded the opening of these meetings to broader participation during the GABs events. This limitation restricted the direct incorporation of external viewpoints and insights into the project's feedback loop.

This broader engagement would have been pivotal for improving the relevance, applicability, and marketability of CONEXUS products, ensuring they meet the diverse needs of a wider audience.

Nevertheless, even within their internal framework, the Harvesting Workshops provided invaluable insights into the development and refinement of CONEXUS products.

2.2 São Paulo Harvesting Workshop

The São Paulo Harvesting Workshop presented an inaugural opportunity for partners to explore the practical applications and market viability of the set of products proposed during the initial phase of the Engine Room. The workshop was structured around a series of pitch rounds, during which representatives from each WP showcased their products to critical allies within the consortium, divided into three groups, acting as proxies for potential end-users and target audiences. These pitch rounds promoted an interactive exchange of feedback and ideas among participants, addressing various aspects such as product packaging, accessibility, and utility. The facilitation of this dynamic dialogue was achieved using paper flip charts and predefined guidelines and questions, enabling each participant to capture and share feedback in real time.

Harvesting Workshop: Engine Room (ER) draft products testing. Guidelines for sketching ER products:

- (i) define one product and its end-user target audience together with the organisations that are part of the WP - each WP is expected to present one product in the Harvesting Workshop;
- (ii) sketch the main concept of the product - what is the topic, what are the important contents, what is the expected impact;
- (iii) define the format (ie. book, video, podcast, app), and describe the expected ways of target-audience interaction with the product;
- (iv) identify which WP will collaborate/deliver inputs to develop the product;
- (v) identify potential challenges & solutions.

Figure 4 Harvesting Workshop guidelines

The workshop was concluded with a plenary discussion, in which the potential products and main outcomes were presented:

- **Inclusive engagement and collective learning in digital times: a handbook for Urban Living Labs**

Format: Handbook

Content:

- a catalogue of tools/methods that organisers can use for different participatory activities, categorised by goal of the activity, and what to pay attention to (e.g. speed-dating and other icebreakers to build connection; language-based breakout rooms to exchange experiences in a meaningful way; Miro or Mural for collaborative mapping/brainstorming; Menti polls to gather data and establish baselines on the spot, etc.);
- a list of crucial roles in these activities (e.g. language mediators, technical support, etc.).

Intended impact: systematisation of knowledge/learnings & methodologies co-created; capacity-building for inclusive and meaningful digital engagement.

Target audiences & how they will interact with the product: Life-Labs multi-stakeholder partnerships to kick-off or strengthen digital activities.

WPs involved and expertise needed: product to be developed by WP3 and WP6 based on project experiences & trialled approaches/methodologies. Potential need of WP1 expertise for template & layout/visual support.

- **Guiding Principles for Co-learning Framework**

Content:

- Five Guiding Principles for Co-learning, based on the concept of Co-production of knowledge, enriched by the concept of Decolonisation of knowledge.
- Description of and infographics for the five principles.
- An operationalisation of T6.2 Principles for co-learning into a self-assessment checklist & tips that organisers can use to make sure activities promote inclusivity.

Intended impact: To deliver co-production of knowledge, we need to learn from one another. Learning across various ontologies and epistemologies demands additional tools than those offered by transdisciplinary research. The aim is to equalise directions of learning and avoiding typical colonising approaches such as north->south, men->women, academia->practice and any other kind of single-directional knowledge transfer. Modifying tool to balance power distribution between marginalised cultures/actors and dominant ones.

Target audience: All consortium members are involved in co-learning and co-production of knowledge. Target audience are organisers of sessions, product developers and researchers.

Potential challenges: Embedding and adopting the principles in all learning events and opportunities, creating space for critical reflection and review within the consortium. The development of a checklist and infographics to relay the main messages of the principles will be a useful tool for embedding and adopting.

WPs involved and expertise needed? Expertise needed: Infographics: WP1 (LALI), Gender group, WP2: Challenging definitions of NbS

- **YouTube Channel**

Format: YouTube channel

Content: Life-Labs and content related videos

Intended impact: Disseminate project outcomes to a broader audience

Target audience: General public

Potential challenges: Little content production to attract engagement to the channel

WPs involved and expertise needed? LL and Tasks with outcomes to disseminate; Content curation and social media management.

- **GIS Web Tool**

Format: Interactive/open GIS web tool

Content: Spatial data analysis (land use, GB Infrastructure, Biodiversity areas, NbS)

Intended impact: Allow data comparison among pilots, give visibility to CONEXUS scientific results, improve understanding urban/environmental conditions

Target audience: Practitioners, Policy-makers

Potential challenges: Data availability and access, lack of appropriated technical infrastructure and financial resources

WPs involved and expertise needed? WP3; GIS, setting online tool

- **Nature-based solutions' contribution to the SDGs Policy Brief: evidence from H2020 Conexus or Nature-based solutions' integrated benefits for sustainability: contributions to the global goals**

Format: Policy brief

Content: review of methodology used to record/map potential NbS contributions to the global goals (SDGs) & evidence generated on Pilots' integrated benefits.

Intended impact: to generate evidence on NbS multidimensional and integrated contributions to (urban) sustainability and resilience, linking local monitoring systems to international frameworks (SDGs) & making the case for investment and business plans. **Target audience & how they will interact with the product:** Policy makers & private sector actors/potential investors. The policy brief could be used to promote NbS policy uptake & encourage investments.

Potential challenges: availability of data and issues with indicators measuring.

WPs involved and expertise needed: Mainly WP6/T6.1. Content inputs from WP4 concerning indicators' measured and processes of data collection will be needed. Graphic layout support will be needed from WP1 as well.

- **Strategic roadmap for accessing funding for urban NbS initiatives**

Format: Interactive roadmap, decision-support tool

Content: A decision tree that gives applicants a path for which funding sources and resources they can consider for their NbS initiative. The roadmap is based on a set of questions for Life-Labs to answer, and links initiatives with funding sources categories and resources/ tools. Tested on 2 Life-Labs in CONEXUS (one CELAC, one EU). The roadmap structures existing knowledge and shares it between the Life-Labs, assisting them to sort through the information available. Three components:

- **A.** Decision tree for an NbS initiatives: A set of approx. 5-8 questions for Life-labs (applicants) to answer. Each question includes a long list of options and alternatives for applicants to check.
- **B.** Resource bank: resources, tools, relevant literature, guides and funding sources (databases and categories rather than specific calls). These are mostly existing resources which we gather into a bank. The guides will need to be developed for more summarised information.
- **C.** Tagging system linking components **A** and **B**: A system to link initiatives and funding/ resources.

Intended impact:

- Assist Life-Labs to scale up and realise their initiatives, linking the questions and issues of Life-Labs with existing knowledge within the consortium.
- Support Life-Labs in creating stronger business cases.
- The tool aims to address the gap between existing funding mechanisms and the challenges and opportunities for NbS fund seekers.

Target audience: LifeLabs in CONEXUS, fund seekers for urban NbS initiatives

Potential challenges:

- Based on existing knowledge of the consortium, no wider approach at this time. T6.2 facilitates knowledge from WP5 and Life-Labs and structures it into a roadmap. T6.2 does not hold specific expertise in the area. Tagging systems in particular, may need additional expertise and input.
- We see this milestone as a structure/ solid base formed on the learnings of the consortium so far, to be further developed and adjusted over the second half of the CONEXUS project.
- The tool is based on existing structures of knowledge, definitions of NbS terminology and published research, which may reinforce a euro-centric framework. T6.2 will review the tool more closely against Guiding Principles of co-learning before submission.
- Funding the right balance to make it of use. The roadmap should be general enough that it should be able to be applied to different contexts (with some adjustments), but instructive enough for practical use at the local and regional level.
- Funding sources change over time. Including specific grants and other concrete fund sources requires long-term maintenance.

WPs involved and expertise needed: Co-learning is promoted between WP5 expertise and context-based experiences and other knowledge systems in the Life-Labs. Expertise needed: Online quiz/ survey development.

- **Introductory guidance for the development of a business case to valorise NbS**

Format: Guidance

Content: Introductory guidance document with step by step guidelines, including a checklist, for the development of a business case to valorise NbS, including 2-3 pilot activities.

Intended impact: Empower local stakeholders to develop their own business cases/plan, familiarise them with NbS and promote upscaling and uptake of NbS as a viable alternative for traditional grey infrastructure projects, develop a transferable methodology for other Life-Labs to valorise their programme

Target audience & how they will interact with the product: Local administrators, community organisations, NGOs, practitioners and other stakeholders that are interested in developing a business case/plan for NbS and to support requests for public/private funding

Potential challenges: As we intend to use some of the Conexus pilot activities as reference cases (2-3), availability of data on the inputs/outputs of the activities, and local capacity to support economic valuation and valorisation

WPs involved and expertise needed: Environmental economist and marketing specialist, knowledge of Ecosystem Services modelling and economic valuation tools. Links with WP 5.1, WP 5.2 and WP 6.2

- **NbS guidance platform**

Format: Guidance

Content: Comprehensible material with low cost, practical step by step solutions with many technical details, cost benefit analysis of NbS, awareness raising communication approaches and governance aspects

Intended impact: Provision of easily accessible NbS guides taking into account language / format, adapted to the local context, different target groups and the stage in the NbS process (design, implementation, operation/ maintenance).

Target audience & how they will interact with the product: Perceived lack of NbS guidance in CONEXUS CELAC Life Lab countries

WPs involved and expertise needed: WP4. Based on Assessment of guidance material from Latin America and Europe: Selection criteria based on needs from LL interviews (e.g. target group, geographical focus, NbS challenge, process phase, guidance type).

By fostering an environment of collaboration and innovation, the Harvesting Workshop laid a solid foundation for the continued evolution of CONEXUS products. Building on the feedback from the consortium partners collected during the workshop, the WP, with the coordination of the Engine Room, started developing the products.

2.3 Turin Harvesting Workshop

The initial Harvesting Workshop in São Paulo set the stage by discussing a prioritised pool of products. At the subsequent Harvesting Workshop in Turin, the attention focused on three particularly promising

products: (i) the Policy Brief Series, (ii) the Co-Learning Principles - a comprehensive framework, and (iii) the Co-Learning Methodology. To facilitate focused discussions, participants were organised into two groups:

- **Group 1: Policy Briefs Breakout room**

Initially, the group provided feedback regarding the format, feasibility, applicability, and attractiveness of the Policy Brief series, also considering the proposed design. In a second phase, the group agreed on a working agenda to commence the production of the policy briefs. This breakout room was directed towards the Life-Labs participants.

During the discussion, challenges faced by Latin America (LA) and practitioners in public management, policy officers, and NbS non-experts were highlighted. There was a noted absence of governance across different levels and a desire to draw lessons from experiences in Turin that could be applied to other cities. The need to create policy briefs that compared single experiences from LA and Europe arose, emphasising the importance of harvesting policy recommendations grounded in reality rather than theory. Participants emphasised the opportunity to share abstracts from policy briefs at the Barcelona conference, with dedicated sessions for co-design where officials and organisations could exchange insights on NbS implementation and governance. A presentation by TUM (T4.3) delineated the differences between factsheets and policy briefs, stressing the need for clear, concise, and impactful content, with a focus on lessons learned and practical recommendations. Participants advocated for multi-language policy briefs and the involvement of local governments beyond CONEXUS if possible. The session concluded with recommendations for structuring policy briefs and suggestions for infographics to enhance their attractiveness.

This is the final list of the twelve produced policy briefs:

1. Barcelona's strategies to increase and enhance urban green infrastructure.
2. Sustainable Urban Drainage Systems: Approach and Experiences in Barcelona
3. Learning from the green infrastructure systems in the City of Bogotá; Connectivity for people and biodiversity
4. Nature Based Solutions for preventing urban sprawl in Latin America: Contributions from Bogotá's Sustainable Urbanisation efforts.
5. Urban Wetland protection and restoration; Learning from Bogotá's conservation and co-management policies.
6. Connectivity for people and biodiversity; Learning from the green infrastructure systems in the City of Bogotá
7. Nature-based strategies to improve livability in vulnerable areas and enhance ecosystems; The innovative approach of Independencia Green Belt, Peru
8. Increasing Community and Stakeholder Engagement in Lisbon's Nature-Based Solutions
9. Integrating Nature-Based Solutions in Planning Instruments; Santiago's case for a city-region multi-stakeholder approach to promote territorial equity and environmental justice.
10. Moving towards greener cities: strategies to develop green spaces in vulnerable neighbourhoods; Santiago's case.
11. Green corridors to connect urban ecosystems; Insights from São Paulo's Municipal Plan for Protected Areas, Green Areas and Open Spaces

12. SDG policy brief “Localising the Sustainable Development Goals: the untapped potential of nature-based solutions in cities”.

For broader dissemination, the layout of the twelve policy briefs will be improved to disseminate them to a wider audience through the CONEXUS website.

- **Group 2: Co-learning Breakout room**

The importance of creating a permeable physical space to foster trust, connections, and collaboration among disparate groups was underscored by lessons learned from virtual work environments, particularly during the COVID-19 pandemic. Additionally, topics like authorship and gender inequality were mentioned, particularly in academic circles, highlighting the need to assess progress toward diversity and inclusivity within NbS initiatives. The concept of colonisation was explored within contemporary contexts, highlighting the need to recognize and rectify power imbalances, especially regarding knowledge ownership and exchange in NbS practices. Co-learning methodologies, seen as replicable formats adaptable to diverse contexts, were proposed as valuable tools for fostering horizontal dialogue and knowledge sharing in the NbS field. These methodologies could be implemented in various domains, including education, with the aim of creating customisable handbooks or guides accessible to different audiences. Language considerations were crucial for effective knowledge expression and co-production in NbS, with efforts required to make academic outputs more accessible and comprehensible to non-researchers. Formats like checklists or step-by-step guides, as exemplified by [ICLEI's user-friendly interface for Urban Greening Plans](#), were suggested for impactful product delivery, emphasising simplicity without sacrificing rigour.

2.4 Products Developed through the Engine Room/Harvesting Workshop

Discussed within the Engine Room, see below the final list of products developed by the CONEXUS consortium:

- Inclusivity and Digital Learning Handbook
- Principles for Co-Learning
- **Data on SDG/NUA impacts/potentials linked with investment propositions uploaded to OPPLA (Deliverable 6.1 Report) Policy Brief Series**
- Factsheet Series
- Valorisation of Nature-based Solutions
- Roadmap for NbS Investment
- Repository of NbS Guidance
- How to set up a Life-Lab? A Guide based on the CONEXUS Life-Labs Experience
- Co-Learning Forum: A Methodology

Inclusivity and Digital Learning Handbook

Inclusive engagement and collective learning in digital times: a handbook for Real Life Labs

Format: Handbook

Status: In progress

[READ MORE](#)

Principles for Co-learning

Guiding principles for co-learning framework

Format: Guiding principles and self-assessment checklist, accompanying resource to Product A1 but also stand-alone product.

Status: In progress

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How NBS contribute to Sustainable Development Goals

Nature-based solutions' contribution to the SDGs: evidence from H2020 Conexus Nature-based solutions' integrated benefits for sustainability: contributions to the global goals

Format: policy brief

Status: In progress

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Policy Brief Series

A series of short publications aimed at decision-makers, public managers, academia and activists, to increase the impact of CONEXUS results on mainstreaming NBS in policy agendas.

Una serie de publicaciones breves dirigidas a los responsables de la toma de decisiones, los gestores públicos, el mundo académico y los activistas, con el fin de aumentar el impacto de los resultados de CONEXUS en la integración de las ENB en las agendas políticas.

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553 of existing green spaces

Factsheet series

A series of short publications on the CONEXUS pilot projects and the key learnings from the different work packages. The factsheets are aimed to increase the impact of the CONEXUS results on the uptake of NBS in practice and, therefore, are focuses on practitioners, professionals, and technicians from municipalities, other governmental institutions, private companies, and NGOs.

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Valorisation of Nature-based Solutions

A step-by-step guidance document designed to support decision-makers in urban areas and funders seeking to invest in NBS. The guidance identifies the monetary value of NBS and their wider societal, environmental, and health benefits.

Status: In progress | Draft document in testing

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Roadmap for NBS Investment

Strategic roadmap for accessing funding for urban NBS initiatives

Format: Interactive roadmap, decision-support tool

Status: In progress

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Repository of NBS Guidance

Inventory of Nature Based Solutions Guidance

Format: Spreadsheet

Status: In progress

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How to set up a Life lab? a guide based on the CONEXUS life labs experience

This guide is intended to provide our own reflections on the steps we followed for setting up the Lifelabs in CONEXUS. We draw inspiration from the Sao Paulo event where we first pitched this product and would like to invite the participation of all partners, but specifically the Life labs leaders so they can help us re-construct their experiences.

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Co-learning Forum – A methodology

A how-to guide for Co-learning Forums - a handbook of key methodology and tools

Format: handbook with a catalogue of methods and tools for processes of co-learning, including a list of crucial roles in these activities.

Status: In progress

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Figure 5 Products display on the Engine Room Website

From the list presented above, CONEXUS partners involved in T6.3, in collaboration with other consortium partners, are finalising the following products to display them on the website and to pursue wider dissemination: (i) Principles of Co-Learning, (ii) Co-Learning Forum - a Methodology, (iii) Policy Briefs Series (a total of 12 policy briefs harvesting policy lessons from CONEXUS LL and partner cities; (iv) Policy brief: “Localising the Sustainable Development Goals: the untapped potential of nature-based solutions in cities”

The Factsheet series was initially discussed under the Engine Room and later developed within WP4, specifically under the Ecosystems of Guidelines (T4.3). Through the articulation of partners of T6.3, the NbS Valorisation Guide developed by WP5 is being tested by two NbS pilots from another Horizon Project

- UPSURGE, one in Budapest, and another in Katowice. This initiative underscores the added value of clustering between projects, facilitating the exchange of insights, methodologies, and outcomes. It enhances the potential for cross-project learning, enabling the adoption and adaptation of successful strategies across different contexts. Such collaboration not only broadens the impact and applicability of individual project outputs but also fosters a more cohesive and integrated approach to addressing complex sustainability challenges through NbS.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the journey of Task 6.3 in designing project products tailored to the project's targeted audience has been marked by a series of challenges, achievements, and valuable lessons. The Engine Room served as a pivotal platform for collaborative product development, allowing consortium partners to co-produce and stress-test CONEXUS end-user products. However, challenges such as GDPR compliance and the lack of PMs for product development were encountered, highlighting the importance of careful planning of collaborative processes and allocation of resources in future project proposals.

The introduction of the Engine Room brought significant added value by centralising discussions in a transparent forum accessible to all consortium members, rather than having these conversations scattered across emails. This approach not only streamlined communication and ensured that valuable insights and decisions were captured systematically but also fostered a culture of openness and collective problem-solving. It created a living archive of the project's intellectual journey, accessible for reflection and learning at any point.

The Harvesting Workshops further enriched the product development process by gathering feedback and critically assessing the market potential of CONEXUS products. Despite logistical constraints limiting broader participation, these workshops provided key insights into the refinement and evolution of CONEXUS products. Overall, the collaborative efforts in developing products like policy briefs, co-learning methodologies, etc., shows the consortium's commitment to fostering innovation and addressing real-world challenges in sustainable urban development.

Annex

São Paulo Harvesting Workshop Screenplay

Date and time: Day 3, Friday 27th May; **10:30**

Venue: Butantã campus, location to be confirmed.

Topic: *Test the products prioritised in the Engine Room*

Background: Within the Harvesting Workshop, partners will think and discuss critically about the practical applications and market potential of the CONEXUS products collected in the Engine Room, in a creative environment to stimulate innovation.

Dynamic of the workshop (pitch-rounds):

- Pitch-rounds will be held, where WP representatives will present the products to the critical allies of the consortium who will represent the potential end users of the products and target audiences.
- Participants will share their feedback and ideas on how the product could be packaged, how it could be useful and easily accessible, etc.
- Each group will have a brown paper over flip charts, where participants can add feedback on the products during the session and after it as well.
- Duration: 1,5 hours.

Goals of the workshop:

- To think critically and discuss practical applications of 6 potential CONEXUS products and the possibilities of making them marketable to end-users.
- To get feedback from partners about products’ requirements, functionalities and formats.

Expected outcomes from the workshop:

- Building on the feedback from the consortium partners collected during the workshop, the WP, with the coordination of the Engine Room, will start developing the products. A work plan will be developed after the SP Conference to coordinate the development of the products, listing deadlines, partner contribution, responsibilities, etc.

DURATION	SESSION TITLE	ACTIVITY / MODERATOR
5´	Welcome words, Introduction, Objectives and explanation of the dynamics of the workshop	PowerPoint Presentation (X) Welcome words: Priscila Objectives: Daniela Explanation of the dynamics of the workshop: Roger
5´	Split up in 3 groups	Time for splitting on tables (Room 1,2,3)
30´	Presentation of the products by each WP leader (1st round)	Collect from each WP the name of a representative, add it to this document and share this draft with them for their info
30´	Presentation of the products by each WP leader (2nd round)	Same as above.
	Coffee break	

40'	Plenary discussion	<p>The representative of each WP does a summary of the discussed points (each has 3 minutes)</p> <p>Guiding questions:</p> <p>a) From the feedback you received in the Harvesting Workshop, how marketable and useful do you think your product will be to the target end-users? b</p> <p>a) Are there any adjustments you might consider doing in the product after the feedback? What?</p> <p>b) How did the workshop contribute to the further development of your product?</p>
1'	Thank you all	Each moderator (Priscila, Daniela and Roger) thanks the attendees for their engagement (each moderator)

São Paulo Harvesting Workshop Photos

Turin Harvesting Workshop Screenplay

Date and time: Day 2, Thursday 26th October; **09:00**

Venue: Open Incet, Piazza Teresa Noce 17

Topic: Test and refine products developed through the Engine Room

Background: Different potential products from CONEXUS are being discussed through the Engine Room. The Harvesting Workshop is the moment where consortium partners have the opportunity to reflect and critically discuss the practical applications, market potential and attractiveness of the products being proposed. A first pool of prioritised products were discussed in the Harvesting Workshop at São Paulo. During this second Harvesting

Workshop, we will approach products that were not yet tested such as: (i) Policy Brief Series; (ii) Co-Learning Principles - a framework; (iii) Co-Learning Methodology.

Goals of the workshop:

- To think critically and discuss practical applications of potential CONEXUS products and the possibilities of making them marketable to end-users;
- To get feedback from partners about products’ requirements, functionalities and formats;
- To agree on a work structure and agenda for the co-creation of Policy Briefs together with the Life-Labs.

Expected outcomes from the workshop:

- Building on the feedback from the consortium partners collected during the two Harvesting Workshops, the Engine Room will facilitate the further development of prioritised products, taking into account partners expertise and capacity, product impact and exploitation potential, and feasibility.

DURATION	SESSION TITLE	ACTIVITY / MODERATOR
05’	Setting the scene	Welcome words, explanation of the workshop, and setting the scene Split up in 2 break-out rooms: (i) Policy Briefs (ii) Inclusive Learning Priscila
60’	Break-out room 1 Policy Briefs Life-Labs	This breakout room will deepen the discussion around the Policy Brief series. First the group will provide feedback in terms of format, feasibility, applicability, and attractiveness of the Policy Brief series, also in relation to the proposed design. In a second moment, the group will agree on a working agenda to start producing the policy briefs. This break-out room is directed to the Life-Labs. Priscila and Kassia, Roger support Main room 20-30 people.
	Break-out room 2 Inclusive Learning	This breakout room will work on two products related to Inclusive Learning: (i) Co-Learning Principles - a framework; and (ii) Co-Learning Methodology. Tbd with Van & Emma Vanessa, Emma, and Federica support Smaller room 15 people. No need for 1 hour only 20 min. How to set a Life Lab
10’	Break	

30'	<p>Plenary discussion</p> <p>First part (10'): 5 minutes each project owner to pitch what the product is about and what improvements were suggested</p> <p>Second part (20'): open discussion - plenary feedback, suggestions.</p>	<p>A representative of each break-out room does a summary of the discussed points. An open round for discussion and feedback will follow.</p> <p>Guiding questions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) <i>From the feedback you received in the Harvesting Workshop, how marketable and useful do you think your product will be to the target end-users?</i> a) <i>Are there any adjustments you might consider doing in the product after the feedback? What?</i> b) <i>How did the workshop contribute to the further development of your product?</i>
15'	Wrap-up and closing	Priscila

Turin Harvesting Workshop Photos

Conexus Life Labs

CONEXUS Life-Labs: local communities of learning, trialling nature-based thinking methods.

CONEXUS Life-Labs - demonstrating NBS and restoring ecosystems in CELAC and EU cities

Lisbon: establishing and diversifying biodiverse green corridors, via NBS innovation based on social enterprise, enhanced habitat allotments and rainwater harvesting in low-income districts and deprived residential areas.

Turin: climate adaptation using NBS at micro and macro levels - extensive tree planting and community design of green retrofits in forgotten spaces (walls, roofs, amenities), for heat, air quality and sustainable drainage.

Barcelona: strategic, international city cooperations and networks (using Barcelona's unique CELAC advocacy role); regreening dense urban and deprived neighbourhoods with urban food and amenity interventions.

Santiago: inclusive green routes, residential eco-landscapes and place-prescribing actions, to connect districts and sports facilities, public facilities and economic centres, for air quality, access, mobility and inclusion.

São Paulo: urban woodland restoration, native species replanting, and creation of blue-green corridors, monitoring for air quality, carbon uptake, health and wellbeing, urban water quality and quantity and heat island amelioration.

Bogotá: peri-urban habitat restoration for sustainable urbanisation: urban food networks, sustainable drainage (SUDS) and wildlife reserves (páramo, forest and riparian land restoration) in urban expansion areas.

Buenos Aires: re-blued and re-greened places in dense urban environments: low-cost vegetated walls and fences built and tested with schools; deculverting and SUDS with land-value capture - for air, heat and flood mitigation.

All cities: Co-creation, place-keeping and valorisation of context-sensitive, biodiverse NBS in Life-Labs, engaging participation of citizens, businesses and stakeholders, testing novel nature-based thinking methods.

Conexus Engine Room Handbook

Conexus Engine Room Handbook

1. You should assume that everything posted in the Engine Room is confidential to the Conexus project and you must not share it externally without the permission of the person posting.
2. The Conexus project fosters inclusivity and the Engine Room is an extension of this; therefore please ensure anything you post is inclusive and open to all.
3. Please ensure all discussions are professional and polite: the Engine Room is a safe space where discussion will remain supportive and inclusive at all times.
4. At the end of each product page there is the opportunity for people to comment and discuss ideas by creating a new discussion thread or responding to an existing comment.
5. The Engine Room uses automatic translation provided by Google Translate. You should check translations with colleagues where there is any doubt about meaning or context.
6. Any downloadable documents or links to draft documents are not automatically translated. Providing translations is the choice and responsibility of each product owner.
7. Although the Engine Room is an internal space it is important to remember that data protection still applies. Sensitive or personal data or any information identifying research participants etc. must not be posted.
8. Everyone in the Conexus project is welcome to propose new products for testing in the Engine Room. Get in touch if you want to add a new product and we will help.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement no. 867564

Project Partners

CONEXUS

Urban nature connects us
 Conectados por la naturaleza urbana
 Conectados pela natureza urbana

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